

BIAXIAL TESTING OF GLASS FIBER REINFORCED MATERIAL SYSTEMS

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SUMMARY: To study the behaviour of fibre reinforced composite laminates under static and cyclic in-plane complex stress states; a biaxial loading frame has been developed. Using four independent servo-hydraulic actuators a cruciform type specimen is biaxially loaded in its plane. During the test an appropriate control unit keeps the centre of the specimen at the same position. For obtaining reliable biaxial failure data the design of the cruciform specimen is of paramount importance. Finite element simulations of the cruciform specimen in combination with experiments using both strain gages and an optical-numerical full field method for strain determination over the entire biaxially loaded test zone have been carried out. This led to the proposal of an optimized geometry with a circular central region of reduced thickness and an adapted corner fillet at the intersection of the arms.

KEYWORDS: A. Polymer-matrix composites (PMCs); B. Mechanical properties; C. Finite element analysis (FEA); D. Non-destructive testing; Biaxial testing of cruciform coupons

INTRODUCTION

Due to their high specific strength and stiffness, the use of fibre reinforced composite materials in any industrial branch has increased rapidly in recent years. In general, these composite laminates mostly in the form of thin shells are developing biaxial or even multiaxial stress states [1,2]. Advances by the composite materials testing community in recent years have resulted in the ability to accurately characterize the uniaxial response of these materials. On the other hand, test methods that can be used to characterize the same materials under multiaxial stress states have not been pursued as rigorously. As a result, there is little existing capability to evaluate the full multiaxial—or even the biaxial—response of composite materials, even though large demand for such information exists [3,4]. The ability to successfully model and simulate the behaviour of materials for optimum use in structural applications, depends largely on the material description (constitutive relations, failure criteria) employed in analytical formulations. The proper choice of constitutive law requires rigorous experimental characterization in order to ensure that the constitutive model adequately describes the behaviour of the material under a variety of complex loading conditions [5]. The current practice of using uniaxial test results to predict failure for multiaxial stress states seems inadequate although numerous failure theories have been

proposed. The lack of reliable biaxial and multiaxial experimental data is directly responsible for preventing this critical step in the evolution of acceptable failure theories [6,7].

Different experimental techniques and specimens have been used to produce biaxial stress states. These techniques may be classified into two categories [8,9]: (i) tests using a single loading system and (ii) tests using two or more independent loading systems. In the first category the biaxial stress ratio depends on the specimen geometry or the loading fixture configuration, whereas in the second category it is specified by the applied load magnitude. Examples of the first category are bending tests on cantilever beams, anticlastic bending tests of flat plates, bulge tests and tests using special fixtures [10-13]. Examples of the second category are a round bar under torsion combined with bending, thin-wall tubes subjected to a combination of tension/compression and torsion or internal/external pressure, and cruciform specimens under in-plane biaxial loading. The technique with the thin-wall tube is the most popular one and seems to be very versatile, because it allows tests with any constant load ratio to be performed. However, it presents some inconveniences [7] as for instance (i) depending on the thickness of the tube and the applied load the radial stress gradients may not be negligible, (ii) real construction components in fibre reinforced composite materials are often flat or gently curved and differ a lot from tubular specimens, (iii) thin-wall tubes are not easy to fabricate, (iv) obtaining a perfect alignment and load introduction is not straightforward, (v) thin tubular specimens can experience various forms of elastic instability when they are subjected to circumferential or axial compression or torsion loads, and (vi) tubes may exhibit changes in geometry during loading, but these effects are usually ignored when processing experimental results. There for the most appropriate method for biaxial testing of fibre reinforced composite laminates consists of applying in-plane biaxial loads to cruciform specimens. In order to do so, a biaxial test device was developed at the Free University of Brussels (VUB) at the Department of Mechanics of Materials and Constructions (MeMC). This device employs four servo-hydraulic actuators for testing cruciform specimens under static and cyclic loading conditions. Finite element simulations of the cruciform specimen geometry in combination with experiments using both strain gages and a full field optical-numerical method for the strain measurements in the biaxially loaded test zone have been carried out, leading to the proposal of an optimized geometry.

PLANE BIAXIAL TEST BENCH FOR CRUCIFORM SPECIMENS

The biaxial test rig, see Figure 1, developed at VUB has a capacity of 100kN in each perpendicular direction, but only in tension, limiting the experimental results to the first quadrant of the two-dimensional stress space.

As no cylinders with hydrostatic bearing were used, failure or slip in one arm of the specimen would result in sudden radial forces which could seriously damage the servo-hydraulic cylinders and load cells. To prevent this, hinges were used to connect the specimen to the load cells and the servo-hydraulic cylinders to the test frame. Using four hinges in each loading direction results in an unstable situation in compression and consequently only tension loads can be applied.

Fig.1. Plane biaxial test device for cruciforms

The stroke of the cylinders is 150mm. The loading may be static or dynamic up to a frequency of 20Hz. Each cylinder is independently controlled and any type of loading waveform, including spectral sequences of variable amplitude, can be efficiently introduced using the dedicated software and control system.

DESIGN OF CRUCIFORM SPECIMEN

A successful biaxial strength test with cruciform specimens required the following conditions: (i) maximization of the region of uniform biaxial strain, (ii) minimization of the shear strains in the biaxially loaded test zone, (iii) minimization of the strain concentrations outside the test zone, (iv) specimen failure in the bi-axially loaded test zone and (v) repeatable results [3,6,14,15]. It has been proven extremely difficult to develop cruciform specimens that simultaneously fulfil all these requirements. If strains are measured at the centre of the specimen using a strain gage or extensometer condition (i) and (ii) have to be fulfilled. Thanks to the development of full field methods for strain determination, non-uniformities in strain and occurring shear strains can be quantified getting round these requirements. The strain symmetry condition however remains to be fulfilled and the strains should at least be constant over the length of the strain gage. Conditions (iii) and (iv) are required if reliable strength data under biaxial loading are needed, avoiding failure in the arms or at the corner fillet of the cruciform specimen. These conditions will be checked by comparing the failure strains obtained on standard beamlike specimens with failure strains on uniaxially loaded cruciform specimens measured at the centre of the specimen. For a suitable cruciform geometry, the failure strain values should be equal indicating no early failure occurred elsewhere in the cruciform specimen.

To investigate the influence of parameters like (i) the radius of the corner fillet at the intersection of the arms, (ii) the thickness of the bi-axially loaded test zone in relation to the thickness of the uniaxially loaded arms and (iii) the geometry of the bi-axially loaded test zone, orthotropic finite element simulations were carried out, allowing a selection of final candidate geometries to be tested experimentally. Afterwards, the numerical results were compared with experimental ones using the digital image correlation technique for full field strain measurements.

MATERIALS AND FINITE ELEMENT SIMULATIONS

The finite element simulations were performed with the commercial software *Ansys* using a plane stress element. It is defined by four nodes having two degrees of freedom at each node: translations in the nodal x and y directions. The element coordinate system was parallel to the global coordinate system. The material modelled was glass fibre reinforced epoxy with a $[(\pm 45/0)_4/\pm 45]_T$ lay-up. The material system and stacking sequence are typical of wind turbine rotor blade construction. Cruciform specimens were machined from plates produced by LM Glasfiber, Denmark, using RTM (resin transfer moulding) technology. When cured, the $[\pm 45]$ plies have a thickness of 0.61 mm and the $[0]$ ones of 0.88 mm. This gives a total thickness of 6.57 mm for the laminate of the cruciform specimen and of 3.59 mm where one group of $[\pm 45/0]$ was milled away at each side of the specimen. Homogenized elastic properties for the composite laminate, derived by means of Classical Lamination Theory, were used for the simulations. The load ratio between the x- and y-directions was chosen equal to the respective strength ratio of the laminate, $F_x/F_y = 46.2 \text{ kN}/12 \text{ kN}$. The width of the arms is 25 mm; the total length of the specimen is 250 mm. In Fig.2, finite element results are shown of the first principal strain for four subsequent geometries. The bi-axially loaded test zone was zoomed in, but the finite element calculations were performed with the arms included.

Fig.2. Finite element results of the first principal strain for four cruciform geometries.

Geometry A is of constant thickness everywhere and has rounded corners with curvature radius of 20 mm. For this geometry the first principal strain is lower in the neighbourhood of the centre of the specimen than in the arms. This is due to the enlargement of the area taking the loads in the central region. Consequently, failure of the specimen will occur in the arms. In order to increase the strains and the likelihood of failure in the bi-axially loaded zone, a reduction of the thickness and/or changing the corner geometry at the intersection of two perpendicular arms was necessary. In geometry B the first suggestion is shown. A square surface of 25 mm by 25 mm with a rounding of 6 mm is milled away. The corner fillet at the intersection of two perpendicular arms remains 20 mm. The magnitude of principal strain increased in the centre of the specimen. If a combination of both suggestions is used, as shown in geometry C where the corner rounding at the intersection of two perpendicular arms is 6.25 mm positioned inside the area of the arms, higher strains are obtained in the bi-axially loaded zone and failure can occur in the centre of the specimen. In geometry D a larger surface is milled away in the central region than in geometry C. Occurrence of failure in the biaxially loaded test zone can only be reached for geometries C and D.

The distribution of in-plane shear strain for the four geometries showed shear strains practically zero in the uniaxially loaded arms and in the centre of the biaxially loaded test zone. Only at the corner fillets small shear strains occurred. Higher values of shear strain were obtained for geometries C and D.

The criterion of the uniformity of the strains over the strain gage length or subset size was studied by considering the distribution of the first principal strain in the most loaded direction over the gage section, which is considered as the milled zone. The normalized value of the principal strain, with respect to that at the centre of the gauge length, over non-dimensional gauge length is shown in Fig.3a. For geometry A no gage section exists, but this was taken equal to the gage section of geometry B of 25 mm diameter. In this zone, zero shear strains are required for coincidence of the applied load directions and principal strain directions. The respective distributions of absolute shear strain values over the relative gage section are presented in Fig.3b.

Fig.3. Strain variation calculated with finite element simulations over the most loaded axis of the gage section.

The first principal strain for the various geometries is almost constant over the gage section. For geometry A the strains are higher at the end of the gage section compared to the centre of the gage section, indicating failure cannot occur in the centre. For geometry B strains are also increasing from the centre towards the ends, but at the end a sudden drop in the strains occurs. For geometry C and D strains show the highest value in the centre and decrease slightly at the ends of the gage section. The most constant strains are obtained for geometry C, with the smallest decrease in strains. For all the geometries the shear strains are close to zero in the biaxially loaded test zone.

EXPERIMENTS USING DIGITAL IMAGE CORRELATION

A full field experimental technique that enables the assessment of the overall strain distribution in the cruciform specimens is absolutely necessary. Strain measurements using a strain gage or extensometer are not sufficient because both give an average value of the deformation along their gauge length. To be able to study the symmetry of the strains and the occurring shear strains experimentally, a full field strain method is necessary.

Digital image correlation (DIC) is an experimental technique, which offers the possibility to determine displacement and deformation fields at the surface of objects under any kind of loading, based on a comparison between images taken at different load steps. A measurement session consists of taking several pictures of the region of interest with a digital camera (1392x1040 pixels). In this case, see Fig.4, two cameras were used to be able to measure both in-plane and out of plane displacements. Each picture corresponds to a different loading step.

Fig.4. Scheme of the video image correlation equipment.

DIC uses an arbitrary speckle pattern that is simply sprayed onto the object surface or that is offered by the texture of the specimen's material. The objective is to obtain an image with a varied and distinctive pattern, in order to enable discrimination between different groups of pixels called subsets. The concept behind the software matching algorithm is that the distribution of grey values in a subset of the picture taken at the undeformed state corresponds to the distribution of grey values of the same subset of the picture taken at the deformed specimen. Possible matches at several locations are checked and a similarity score (correlation function) is used to grade them. A classic correlation function using the sum of the squared differences of the pixel values is used. By tracking the subsets in each successive image, relative displacements are obtained and the resulting strains can be calculated [15,16].

Fig. 5. Digital image correlation results of the first principal strain for four cruciform geometries.

The same cruciform geometries as studied in the finite element simulations were tested experimentally. Results for the first principal strain are shown in Fig.5. Similar distribution of the strain is obtained as in the finite element simulations. Only in the transition zone between the intact laminate and the milled area, high strains are observed with the digital image correlation technique but not in the finite element simulations. This is due to the fact that the milling requires more detailed finite element models to simulate the decrease in number of layers gradually.

Also for the shear strain distributions similar results as in the finite element simulations were found.

The criterion of the uniformity of the strains over the biaxially loaded test zone was also studied experimentally by considering the distribution of the first principal strain over the relative gage section shown in Fig.6a. Shear strain distributions are presented in Fig. 6b.

Fig.6. Strain variation measured with digital image correlation over the most loaded axis of the gage section.

The sudden increase in first principal strain for geometry B and D at a distance of half the gage length is due to high strains obtained for the transition region between the full thickness of the specimen and the milled surface. For geometry C a similar increase can be noticed, but farer away from the centre of the specimen at a distance of about three fourth of the gage section. Experimentally the most uniform cruciform specimen is geometry C. For all the geometries the shear strains are quite constant. The values are close to zero for geometry A till C, for geometry D the values are bigger. Only at the end of the gage section, shear strains are observed for the geometries with a milled surface.

Table 1 presents strain measurements for a load level of $F_x/F_y=46.2\text{kN}/12\text{kN}$ obtained in x- and y- direction by using rosette strain gages of 6 mm length glued in the centre of each specimen and by digital image correlation over the same zone.

Table 1 Strain values obtained with strain gages and DIC.

	strain gages		DIC	
	ϵ_x	ϵ_y	ϵ_x	ϵ_y
Geometry A	1.08	-0.36	1.18	-0.37
Geometry B	1.38	-0.57	1.50	-0.57
Geometry C	1.80	-0.43	1.80	-0.42
Geometry D	2.10	-0.57	2.11	-0.59

EXPERIMENTS USING STRAIN GAGES FOR FAILURE DATA

To decide which geometry to prefer, experimental biaxial failure results are needed. The results of strain gages glued in the centre of the specimen are used for this. The experimental results for the four tested geometries loaded at different ratios are shown in Fig.7a. Both the results of the cruciform specimens and beamlike specimens are shown.

Fig.7. Biaxial failure results in strain space.

The highest failure strains are obtained for geometry C, again indicating this geometry is the most suitable one. In Fig.7b the failure strains are shown only for this geometry together with the failure strains obtained on beamlike specimens. The failure strains of this geometry for the uniaxial load ratios are similar to the failure strains of the standard beamlike specimens, indicating no early failure of the cruciform geometry occurred before failure in the specimen's centre.

CONCLUSIONS

The combination of finite element simulations and experiments performed on different cruciform geometry types using the digital image correlation technique for full field strain measurements, led to the selection of a suitable geometry for bi-axial testing of fibre reinforced composite laminates. This geometry has a reduced thickness in the central region of the specimen, in combination with a fillet corner between two arms inside the material. These features cause failure to occur in the bi-axially loaded test zone, rather than in the uniaxially loaded arms giving failure strains comparable to strains obtained on beamlike specimens for the uniaxial load ratios. The digital image correlation technique used for full field strain measurements offers significant advantages over conventional techniques such as strain gauges. The spatially resolved strains led to a better understanding of the behaviour of composites under bi-axial loads. The strain values obtained with the digital image correlation technique are comparable with those calculated in the finite element simulations.

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